

The Communicative Language Teaching Approach

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Abstract:

Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) is a language teaching method that emphasizes the importance of communication in real-world situations. CLT focuses on developing students' communicative competence, or their ability to use language effectively and appropriately in different social contexts. CLT does this by engaging students in authentic and interactive learning activities that focus on fluency and appropriateness in communication. CLT also de-emphasizes writing skills and grammatical aspects of communication, and instead emphasizes message and meaning. This paper attempts to highlight the perspective on language and learning, strong and weak versions of Communicative Language Teaching Approach, its features, classroom procedures etc.

Keywords: Communicative, audio - lingual, drilling, comprehensible pronunciation

Introduction:

What Is The Communicative Language Teaching Approach?

The basic idea that communicative ability is the goal of foreign language learning is not a new one. The structural approach and the audio-lingual method also stressed communicative ability. "If developments since the 1970s have special claim to the label 'communicative', it is because the implications of this goal have been explored more thoroughly and explicitly than before." The communicative approach to language teaching is based on the belief that acquiring a language means to communicate confidently and fluently in the language.

Perspective on Language and Language Learning:

The communicative approach opens up a wider perspective on language. The main characteristics of the communicative view of language are:

- Language is a system for the expression of meaning.
1. The primary function of language is for interaction and communication.
 2. The structure of language reflects its functional and communicative uses.
 3. The primary units of language are not merely its grammatical and structural features, but categories of functional and communicative meaning as exemplified in discourse.

A communicative approach opens up a wider perspective on language learning. it makes us more strongly aware that in particular, to manipulate is not enough to teach learners structures of the foreign language. They must also develop strategies for relating these structures to their communicative functions in real situations and real how time"

Strong and Weak Versions:

There are two versions of Communicative Language Teaching Approach (CLTA) strong and weak. Howatt distinguishes between the two versions in the following words:

"There is in a sense, a 'strong' version of the

communicative approach and a 'weak' version. The weak version which has become more or less standard practice in the last ten years, stresses the importance of providing learners with opportunities to use their English for communicative purposes and characteristically, attempts to integrate such activities into a wider program of language... The 'strong' version of communicative teaching, on the other hand, advances the claim that language is acquired through communication, so that it is not merely a question of activating an existing but inert knowledge of the language, but of stimulating the development of the language system itself. If the former could be described as 'learning to use' English, the later entails 'using English to learn it.'

Features of Communicative Approach:

The major distinctive features of the communicative approach as contrasted with the audio-lingual method are the following:

1. Meaning is paramount.
2. Dialogues, if used, centre around communicative functions and are not normally memorized.
3. Contextualization is a basic premise.
4. Language learning is learning to communicate.
5. Effective communication is sought.
6. Drilling may occur, but peripherally.
7. Comprehensible pronunciation is sought.
8. Any device which helps the learners is accepted-varying according to their age, interest etc.
9. Attempts to communicate may be encouraged from the very beginning.
10. Judicious use of native language is accepted where feasible.
11. Translation may be used where students need or benefit from it.
12. Reading and writing can start from the first day, if desired.
13. The target linguistic system will be learned best through the process of struggling to communicate.
14. Communicative competence is the desired goal

(i.e., the ability to use the linguistic system effectively and appropriately).

15. Linguistic variation is a central concept in materials and methodology.
16. Sequencing is determined by any consideration of content, function, meaning which maintains interest.
17. Teachers help learners in any way that motivates them to work with the language.
18. Language is created by the individual after thorough trial and error.
19. Fluency, and acceptable language is the primary goal: accuracy is judged not in the abstract but in context.
20. Students are expected to interact with other people, either in the flesh, through pair and group work, or in their writings.
21. The teacher cannot know exactly what language the students will use.
22. Intrinsic motivation will spring from an interest in what is being communicated by the language.

Classroom Procedures:

In most traditional classrooms, the common classroom procedure is whole-class work. In communicative language teaching, the main types of organisation are individual work, pair work, small group work and whole class work.

The advantages of pair work and small group work are:

- (i) Pupils get more language practice. They have to speak more English than they would otherwise do if the work is done 'round the class'.
- (ii) Pupils are active participants. They are more involved in learning. If some discussion is done in the whole class, only the bright pupils will take interest in it whereas others will lose it.
- (iii) Pupils feel secure. They feel less anxiety when they are working in pairs or small groups than when they are 'on show' in front of the whole class.
- (iv) Pupils help each other. They share ideas and knowledge.

These classroom procedures have certain problems.

- (i) The pair work and group work are generally noisy. It is, however, pointed out that pupils themselves are not disturbed by this noise. Further, it is purposeful noise: pupils are using English. Since pupils have to communicate with one another, a certain amount of noise cannot be avoided. The teacher should ask the pupils not to shout.
- (ii) Pupils make mistakes. The teacher cannot watch the performance of all the pairs or groups. The number of mistakes can be reduced by providing enough preparation and by checking.
- (iii) The teacher has less control over what pupils are doing in the class. To overcome this difficulty, it is suggested that he should give

clear instructions to the pupils about when to start, what to do, and when to stop.

Role of the Teacher:

In communicative language teaching, the teacher needs to adopt a variety of roles. These include the following:

- (i) As a general overseer to his students' learning, the teacher must aim to coordinate the activities so that they form a coherent progression, leading towards greater communicative ability.
- (ii) As a classroom manager, he is responsible for grouping activities into 'lessons' and for ensuring that these are satisfactorily organised at a practical level.
- (iii) In many activities, he may perform the familiar role of a language instructor: he will present new language, exercise direct control over the learners' performance, evaluate and correct it, and so on.
- (iv) In others, he will not intervene after initiating the proceedings, but will let learning take place through independent activity or pair and group work.
- (v) When such an activity is in progress he may act as consultant or adviser, helping where necessary. He may also move about the classroom in order to monitor the strengths and weaknesses of the learners, as a basis for planning future learning activities.
- (vi) He will sometimes wish to participate in an activity as-communicator with the learners. In this role, he can stimulate and present new language without taking the main initiative for learning away from the learners themselves.

Advantages of Communicative Approach:

The following are the advantages of the communicative approach:

1. **More language practice:** Pupils get more language practice. As most of the work in the communicative language approach is done in pairs and small groups, pupils have more opportunities to interact in the foreign language.
2. **More involvement:** Pupils are more involved in learning. They feel secure and do not feel shy of speaking English in a small group. Thus, they get confidence to speak the language. They share their ideas with others. They get more opportunities to express their own individuality.
3. **Fluency in speech:** As pupils concentrate on speaking English, they become fluent speakers. They learn the appropriate use of language.
4. **Co-operative relationships:** The teacher's role in the teaching learning process is less dominant. There are more opportunities for co-operative relationships to emerge, both between the teacher and pupils, and among pupils.

Problems and Limitations:

Some of the problems and limitations of the communicative approach are as follows:

1. **Teacher's competence:** It is doubtful, whether an average teacher of English can make a success of this approach. Some teachers themselves cannot speak English fluently. In any case the teacher has to be reoriented to use the new approach.
2. **Neglect of reading and writing skills:** With its over-emphasis on oral communication the communicative approach neglects reading and writing skills. This drawback needs to be removed.
3. **Over-crowded classes:** The Indian classrooms are overflowing with pupils. It is not easy to seat them properly for pair work and group work.
4. **Unanswered questions:** According to Richards' and Rodgers the following questions regarding the communicative approach are still debated:
 - (i) Can the communicative approach be applied at all levels in a language programme?
 - (ii) Is communicative approach equally suited to ESL (English as a second language) and EFL (English as a Foreign Language) situations?
 - (iii) Does the communicative approach require grammar-based syllabuses to be abandoned or merely revised?

Conclusion:

CLT is based on the idea that learning a language successfully comes through having to communicate real meaning. When learners are involved in real communication, their natural strategies for language acquisition are used, which allows them to learn and use the language. CLT also provides a greater room for individual interpretation and variation, and encourages learners to be active agents and negotiators who contribute in a cooperative atmosphere. It is a language teaching method that moved away from individual linguistic structures to teaching people how to use language effectively when communicating. This method is inclined towards fluency and not merely towards accuracy. It aims to develop learner's competence to communicate fluently in the target language. This method stresses the interdependence of language and communication. It highlights the importance of authentic communication in a real context. This method makes learners confident to communicate by getting involved in real communication

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